

SWARMING AND PAIRING BEHAVIOR IN ANACANTHOTERMES TURKESTANICUS

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In higher termites belonging to the family Termitidae, as well as certain species within the family Rhinotermitidae, it is solely the female that attracts males. Upon shedding her wings, the female adopts a specific calling posture, raising her abdomen vertically while evertting the sternal and tergal glands. Once the potential mates encounter each other, they form a tandem, with the female consistently leading. Through experiments and observations of *Trinervitermes bettonianus* (Sjostedt), it has been demonstrated that the tergal gland secretes a pheromone with a considerable range, inducing directed movement of the male from up to 20 cm away. Furthermore, the secretion from the sternal gland serves to lay down an odorous trail utilized during the movement of both solitary females and tandems[1].

Lower termites demonstrate a diverse range of post-flight behaviors. Some species exclusively exhibit tandem behavior, while others solely engage in calling behavior. Additionally, certain species display both calling behavior and tandem behavior. In the adult stage of termites belonging to the Hodotermitidae family, the tergal gland is absent, and the production of sex pheromones occurs solely through the sternal gland. Immediately following the shedding of their wings, males of *Hodotermitidae mossambicus* (Hagen) commence burrowing in the first suitable location while simultaneously adopting a calling posture, emitting a long-range pheromone from the sternal gland. The female can detect this pheromone from distances of up to two meters [1]. However, the behaviors of trail-laying and tandem formation do not occur in this species.

Despite the abundance of research on the biology and behavior of *Anacanthotermes ahngerianus* Jacobson and *A. turkestanicus* Jacobson, native to Uzbekistan, a comprehensive description of the post-flight behavior of these species' adults remains elusive. Some scholars have observed that male *A. turkestanicus* track females by following scent trails (Jacobson, 1904), while females of *A. ahngerianus* may assume a calling posture[2].

These observations might suggest that females of *A. turkestanicus* attract males through trail-laying, whereas *A. ahngerianus* emit airborne sex pheromones[4,5,6]. However, such marked differences in behavior between these species seem improbable and warrant careful

verification, particularly given their natural interbreeding and confirmed experimental hybridization[3]. Our laboratory experiments utilizing extracts from the sternal glands of winged termites *A. turkestanicus* and *A. ahngerianus* have revealed that these glands produce substances acting as trail-following pheromones. Furthermore, the secretion from one sex's gland was found to be attractive to the other. These experiments provide strong evidence for the species specificity of the pheromone. Although sex pheromones have been identified in males and females of *A. ahngerianus* and *Z. nevadensis*, the mating mechanism and adult behavior of these species remain insufficiently explored. The experiment was conducted by catching male and female termites while they were escaping from their nest in order to do swarming. Below pictures are female and male adult termites (picture 1)

Picture № 1

Abdomen part of female of
*A. turkestanicus*Abdomen part of male of
A. turkestanicus

Therefore, our study aims to investigate the behavior and chemical signaling characteristics of sexually mature imagoes of *Anacanthotermes turkestanicus*.

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